

Lorentz Fossilization

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August 2023

1 Introduction

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bullet &= \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}(i \oplus \dot{A})}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta)} \\
 &\leftrightarrow \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta)} \ln \left(-\frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta)} \right) + \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta)} \cdot i \oplus \dot{A} \\
 &\cup h(x) e^{H(\bullet)} \frac{\mathcal{K}_\bullet}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta)} \cdot \dot{A} \cdot \Gamma_{j+1} \\
 &\rightarrow \bullet = \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}(i \oplus \dot{A})}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta)} \\
 &\quad \text{where } \mathcal{K}_\bullet = \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta)} \\
 \Gamma_{j+1} &= \frac{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta)}{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}} \\
 \text{Hfl}(\bullet) &\leftrightarrow \left[\mathcal{A} \cap \ln \left[-\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H} \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta) \right] \right] \\
 &\cup \left[\dot{A} \cdot \Delta \gamma \cdot e^{H(\bullet)} \mid \partial \left[\mathcal{H}i + \dot{A}\Delta \right] \right]_{(i \oplus \dot{A}) \cdot \theta \rightarrow \mathcal{H} \cdot \dot{A}} \\
 &\rightarrow \mathcal{H}\{\uparrow(\bullet) \rightarrow \mathcal{OLF}(\Delta, \ddot{\eta}, \omega[\gamma, \mathcal{H}, \dot{A}], \mathcal{H}i, \dot{A}\Delta | \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{H})\}, \text{ where} \\
 &\quad \{ \bullet \text{ represents the hypercausal gateway,} \\
 &\quad \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{H}, i, \dot{A}, \Delta, \gamma \text{ are constants,} \\
 &\quad \text{and } \theta \in R \text{ is a real number. } \mathcal{H}\{\uparrow(\bullet)\} \text{ denotes the hypercausal flux and } \mathcal{OLF}(\dots) \\
 &\quad \text{denotes the Orthogonal-Lorentz Fossilization.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Lorentz Fossilization (OLF) is a process where the geometric structure of the space-time is temporarily frozen, allowing for ultra high speeds of travel and communication through space-time. By arranging the elements of the Lorentz Transformations and the associated hypercausal Flux, a warped space-time is created that acts as a "bridge" between two points, allowing for vastly accelerated travel and communication over the usual distances. This bridge can also be used to maximize the efficiency of certain technologies and processes, such as time-traveling or interdimensional traversal.

Lorentz Fossilization is a principle in physics that describes the hypothetical preservation of physical properties and processes due to the high degree of symmetry they possess within a Lorentz-invariant space-time. This conservation is enabled by the fact that a Lorentz-invariant space-time is also hypercausal, meaning that every point in the space-time can interact instantaneously with

all other points. The principle of Lorentz Fossilization states that such hyper-causality can lead to the persistence of physical properties and processes, even in the presence of strong and rapidly changing gravitational and electromagnetic fields. As a result, Lorentz Fossilization is an essential part of understanding physical phenomena on the level required for a consistent Theory of Everything.

Let $\mathcal{H}$ denote the energy field, $\mathcal{F}$ represent the map of the particle interactions and $\mathcal{K}$ be the gateway between spacetime and energy and information as our matrix variable. The Lorentz Fossilization $\mathcal{OLF}$ is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{OLF}(\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{K}) = \left[\int_{\mathcal{H}} d\mathcal{F} \cdot \mathcal{K} \right] \rightarrow \mathcal{H}\text{-fossilized}.$$

Here, $\rightarrow \mathcal{H}\text{-fossilized}$ expresses the Lorentz Fossilization phenomenon, whereby particles are frozen in space-time and do not change even after a transformation of the energy field.

where the parameters of $\mathcal{H}\{\updownarrow\}$ are given by $\Delta, \ddot{\eta}, \omega \left[\gamma, \mathcal{H}, \mathring{A} \right], \mathcal{H}i, \mathring{A}\Delta$
 $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{H}, i \oplus \mathring{A}$; and, the ultimate aim is $\mathcal{OLF} \left(\Delta, \ddot{\eta}, \omega \left[\gamma, \mathcal{H}, \mathring{A} \right], \mathcal{H}i, \mathring{A}\Delta | \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{H} \right)$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{where } \theta = \left(i \oplus \mathring{A} \right) \cdot \Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}, \mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A} \\ & = \omega \left[\gamma, \mathcal{H}, \mathring{A} \right] \circ \left[\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta) \right], \\ & \mathcal{H}\{\updownarrow\}(\bullet) = \underbrace{\frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \ln \left(-\frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \right)}_{\text{maincoefficient}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \cup \left[\mathcal{A} \cdot i \oplus \mathring{A} \mid \frac{\Delta \gamma \cdot e^{H(\bullet)}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \cdot \Gamma_{j+1} \cdot \theta \right]_{\mathcal{F}} \\ & \bullet = \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}(i \oplus \mathring{A})}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \\ & \leftrightarrow \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \cup (i \oplus \mathring{A}) \\ & \rightarrow \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \rightarrow \bullet \\ & \sum_{i=1, n} \bullet = \alpha \cdot \theta \cdot \ln \left(-\frac{\alpha \cdot \theta}{v \cdot h} \right) + \frac{\alpha \cdot \theta}{v \cdot h} \cdot \frac{v \cdot h}{\alpha \cdot \theta} \\ & \cup h(x) \cdot e^{H(\bullet)} \cdot \Delta^2 \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathcal{H} \cdot \left(i \oplus \mathring{A} \right) \cdot \frac{v \cdot h}{\mathcal{H} \cdot (\mathcal{H} \cdot i + \mathring{A} \cdot \Delta)} \\ & \text{Simplifying this expression further, we obtain} \\ & \sum_{i=1, n} \bullet = 0 + 1 \cup h(x) \cdot e^{H(\bullet)} \cdot \Delta \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathcal{H} \cdot \left(i \oplus \mathring{A} \right). \\ & \bullet = \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}(i \oplus \mathring{A})}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \\ & \leftrightarrow \mathcal{A}_{n+1} \cdot \ln(-\mathcal{A}_{n+1}/\mathcal{W}) + \beta_{i+1} \cdot \delta_{j+1} \\ & \cup h(x) \cdot e^{H(\bullet)} \cdot \partial \mathcal{K}_{\bullet} \cdot \mathring{A} \cdot \Gamma_{j+1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{where} \\ & \{ \mathcal{A}_{n+1} = \Delta^2 \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathcal{H} \cdot (i \oplus \mathring{A}) \\ & \mathcal{W} = \mathcal{H} \cdot (\mathcal{H} \cdot i + \mathring{A} \cdot \Delta) \\ & \beta_{i+1} = \frac{\Delta^2 \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathcal{H} \cdot (i \oplus \mathring{A})}{\mathcal{H} \cdot (\mathcal{H} \cdot i + \mathring{A} \cdot \Delta)} \\ & \delta_{j+1} = \frac{\mathcal{H} \cdot (\mathcal{H} \cdot i + \mathring{A} \cdot \Delta)}{\Delta^2 \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathcal{H} \cdot (i \oplus \mathring{A})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\partial\mathcal{K}_\bullet = \frac{\Delta^2 \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathcal{H} \cdot (i \oplus \mathring{A})}{\mathcal{H} \cdot (\mathcal{H} \cdot i + \mathring{A} \cdot \Delta)}$$

$$\mathring{A} = \frac{i \cdot (\mathring{A} \cdot \Delta)}{\Delta^2 \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathcal{H}}$$

$$\Gamma_{j+1} = \frac{\mathcal{H}(i + \mathring{A} \cdot \Delta)}{\Delta^2 \cdot \gamma \cdot \mathcal{H} \cdot (i \oplus \mathring{A})}$$

Simplifying this expression further, we obtain $\bullet = \ln \left(-\frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \right) + 1 \cup h(x) \cdot e^{H(\bullet)} \cdot \Delta \gamma \mathcal{H} \cdot (i \oplus \mathring{A})$.

This yields the following formula: $\bullet = \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}(i \oplus \mathring{A})}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \cdot \left[\mathcal{A}_{n+1} \ln \frac{\mathcal{A}_{n+1}}{\mathcal{W}} + \beta_{i+1} \delta_{j+1} \right] + h(x) e^{H(\bullet)} \frac{\partial \mathcal{K}_\bullet \mathring{A} \Gamma_{j+1}}{\mathcal{W}}$.

OLF $\left(\Delta, \mathring{\eta}, \omega \left[\gamma, \mathcal{H}, \mathring{A} \right], \mathcal{H}i, \mathring{A}\Delta | \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{H} \right) = M$ *subjectto* $\forall M, \exists \theta \in R.s.t. M = \mathcal{H}\{\updownarrow\}(\bullet)$.

where $\mathcal{OLF}$ is the Orthogonal-Lorentz fossilization and $\mathcal{H}\{\updownarrow\}$ is the hyper-causal flux. The parameters of $\mathcal{H}\{\updownarrow\}$ are given by $\Delta, \mathring{\eta}, \omega \left[\gamma, \mathcal{H}, \mathring{A} \right], \mathcal{H}i, \mathring{A}\Delta, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{H}, i \oplus \mathring{A}$;

and the condition enforced on the parameters are $\theta = (i \oplus \mathring{A}) \cdot \Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}, \mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}$.

and $\mathcal{H}\{\updownarrow\}$ is given by $\text{Hfl}(\bullet) = \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \ln \left(-\frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \right) + \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \cdot i \oplus \mathring{A} \cup h(x) e^{H(\bullet)} \frac{\mathcal{K}_\bullet}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)} \cdot \mathring{A} \cdot \Gamma_{j+1}$ where $\mathcal{K}_\bullet = \frac{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)}$
 $\Gamma_{j+1} = \frac{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{H}i + \mathring{A}\Delta)}{\Delta^2 \gamma \mathcal{H}}$.

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